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REVAMPING CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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India has the largest population of children and youth worldwide. Its young man power, if educated and skilled, could help and support several ageing nations in the near future. A favourable demography comprising 54 percent of a massive 1.4 billion population below 25 years, are indeed astonishing number for manpower planners, particularly of developed nations. Imagine what would be the cognitive capital if 85-90 percent of schools become truly functional! as Secondary education commission (1964-66) has rightly observed."

"Even the best curriculum and the most perfect syllabus remains dead unless quickened into life by the right methods of teaching and the right kind of teachers."

In traditional pedagogy, the role of a teacher is of a 'sage on the stage'. Teacher spends most of his class room time lecturing, with students listening and taking notes. The comprehension of students is tested by prescribing home work and projects. Now the scenario has changed from 'sage' to Guide by his side. Classroom sessions are utilized to encourage peer-to-peer learning, promoting critical thinking, problem solving etc. The advantages of switching to new classroom management model are:

- Self paced learning
- Multiple ways of learning
- Better time utilization
- Student centered learning
- Better learning outcomes.

There are certain inbuilt problems with regard to class room management such as:

1. Lack of motivation
2. No qualitative check on aptitude, attitude and basic skills of the child.
3. Lack of competent teachers.
4. Examination oriented education system
5. Old traditional curriculum.

Measures to enhance Classroom management

- Encouraging pupils to participate.
- Fostering collaborative approach in teaching & learning.
- Innovative teaching techniques.
- Enhancing thinking & sharing.
- Bridging the gap between theory and practice.
- Adoption of 'Action Research Model' by teachers.
- Supportive, personalized and relevant learning.
- Professional development of teachers.

Thus effective class room management demands:

- Openness: Whole hearted sharing of ideas and intellectual property is the very crucial aspect of effective class room environment.
- Peering: It is the freedom that any individual gets to modify and make changes according to newer ideas provided it is open to others to avail. It is termed as horizontal management or self management.
- Sharing: The knowledge generated is shared by other similar institutions for effective class room management. Some extent of control is allowed to safeguard one's identity.
- Acting globally: Web-based communication service allows different countries to be part of such collective activities which is cost effective in every aspect like geographical boundaries, access of many countries, availability of necessary technology etc.

Teacher's Professional Expertise

Teacher has to go extra mile to prepare the students for real life situations and to meet the challenges of present day. For this, a programme of action is suggested for effective learning.

- Planning a sequence of lessons to ensure learning progress.
- Evaluation of previous lessons.
- Planning and preparation for the lesson.
- Teacher's ability to capture & hold the interest of the class, to establish their authority.
- Deal with and resolve conflict effectively and fairly.
- Good communication with pupils.
- Secure subject knowledge.
- Demonstrating confidence and direction in managing pupil.
- Providing lively, well paced lessons.
- Understanding and meeting the learning needs of all pupils.
- Acting on your reflections and evaluation of previous lessons.

It is important to develop certain classroom leadership skills which contribute to establish a well-organised environment for learning, forge positive relationships with all pupils and establish a classroom ethos which allow pupils to demonstrate positive behaviour and optimum attainment. They are:

- Motivation: Teacher needs to provide time at the start of each lesson to tell pupils what they are learning and why. Pupils need to be involved at every stage.
- Emotional well-being: to help reduce pupil's anxiety teacher should share the lesson structure with pupils at the start, so that they know what is going to happen during the lesson.
- Expectations: Teacher should make clear to the pupils what behaviours are needed for learning activities to be successful.

Teaching has to be whole hearted not half hearted! Can anyone live with half- a heart?

Just as an individual would not remain alive with half-a-heart, half hearted teaching would be "dead teaching." Learning is essentially a process of transformation. A virtuous character is the end product of a process of unfolding of human perfection within. When this is achieved during the moulding period of the child, it is reflected in the conduct of the individual in the years to come.

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Teaching and learning is a process of transformation which is beautifully reflected in the following poem:

I took a piece of clay

And idly fashioned it one day

And as my fingers pressed it still

It moved and yielded to my will,

I took a piece of living clay and gently formed it day by day

And moulded it with power and art

A young child' heart.

It came again when years were gone. It was a man I looked upon. He still that early impress bore. I could change that form no more.

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